

Organising More ERUA Open Science Meet-Ups: New Methods and Experiences from the Re:ERUA Project

1. Introduction

The multi-faceted field of Open Science is subject to constant change and innovation. It thus goes without saying that Open Science-related exchange is paramount as only through exchange can those involved in Open Science learn from each other, design joint measures and thus develop the movement on a collaborative basis without (regularly) reinventing the wheel. Along similar lines, low-threshold formats of exchange are crucial when it comes to introducing (academic) players with little or no Open Science-related pre-knowledge to the movement, its scope and its objectives, thus fostering the movement's principles on a larger scale.

Due to all that and as described in *Organising the ERUA Open Science Meet-Ups: Methods, Experiences and Lessons from the First Ten Months* (Heber, 2023), the deliverables of project Re:ERUA (European Commission, 2024), which aimed at developing the research trajectory of ERUA, the *European Reform University Alliance's* (n.d.), involved the creation of a series of monthly virtual meet-ups (*Open Science Meet-Ups*, n.d.). The idea was to target this series of meet-ups on a low-threshold basis to all ERUA members with Open Science-related interests so everyone interested in Open Science could participate as they pleased without prior registration to discuss current topics, to get feedback on aspects they were working on and to ask questions they were pondering.

In the above-mentioned publication, we elaborated on how we conceptualised this series of meet-ups, how we got them started, how we spread the word on the first nine meet-ups and how we implemented the individual sessions. In this vein, we reflected critically on our experiences, sharing which lessons we learned planning and organising these first nine meet-ups. As the Re:ERUA project has come to a close in September 2024, we want to pick up this thread, revisiting the 19 meet-ups we performed after the ones discussed in *Organising the ERUA Open Science Meet-Ups*. Doing so, we want to elaborate on whatever structural measures we implemented since the first publication, reflecting critically on our

experiences. At the same time, we shall discuss where we chose to maintain previously established frameworks, elaborating on the individual meet-up sessions. The subsequent table provides an overview on all virtual meet-ups performed after the ones discussed in *Organising the ERUA Open Science Meet-Ups*. For disambiguation-related reasons, the numeration picks up where the first publication left off. In two occasions, the table mentions that we performed no virtual meet-ups due to live meet-ups taking place in Roskilde and Vilnius. These live meet-ups were special iterations that took place at the annual ERUA Summits, an annual conferences series that brought together academic players from all over ERUA. In the months when the summits took place, we usually did not offer additional virtual meet-ups for saturation-related reasons. For spatial reasons, we will not elaborate on these live meet-ups here, a publication on our experiences conceptualising and performing the live iterations is currently in progress.

Table 1: Overview of the Open Science Meet-Ups performed after Organising the ERUA Open Science Meet-Ups

List of Virtual ERUA Open Science Meet-Ups		
Nr.	Topic	Date
10	Repositories	24.11.2022
11	Christmas Meet-Up: Recap, Outlook and Christmas Game	15.12.2022
12	Digital Procedures for Citation Analysis	26.01.2023
13	Open Science and the Reform Universities' Paradigm	23.02.2023
14	Open Access Consortia	30.03.2023
15	Teaching Open Science	19.04.2023
16	Performing Open Science	23.05.2023

17	Open Science Information Portal	22.06.2023
18	Open Science Summer Game	27.07.2023
-	<i>No Meet-Up in August due to Summer Break</i>	-
19	Data Quality	21.09.2023
-	<i>No Meet-Up in October due to Live Meet-Up in Roskilde</i>	-
20	Virtual Research Environments (VRE)	23.11.2023
21	Christmas Meet-Up: Open Science and Christmas Game	14.12.2023
22	Pitfalls of Open Access and How to Handle Them	25.01.2024
23	Research Data Management and Open Science	22.02.2024
24	Better Together – The Political and Networking Dimension of Research Data Management	21.03.2024
25	Research Data Management Across Countries	25.04.2024
26	Open Educational Resources within the ERUA Open Science Ambassador Programme: A Best Practice Example	23.05.2024
-	<i>No Meet-Up in June due to Live Meet-Up in Vilnius</i>	-
27	Open Science Summer Game Reloaded	25.07.2024
28	Three Years of European Universities Initiative Open Science: Recap and Outlook	26.09.2024

2. Turning the Meet-Ups' Concept into a Standard Structure

Over the course of the first meet-ups, we gradually developed the standard structure delineated in Table 2. This structure involves a tripartite form revolving around an

average meet-up time frame of 45 minutes. Satisfied with how that structure worked out, we decided to stick with it. The same goes for the meet-ups' regularity, which is why we decided to stick with every month's last Thursday afternoon as the usual meet-up time established during the first nine meet-ups. While most meet-ups did follow these principles, we ought to mention that there were several exceptions, such as the Open Science-related games we occasionally played. We will elaborate on the individual sessions in one of the next subchapters.

Table 2: Structure of an average meet-up

Duration	Phase	Purpose
5 – 10 minutes	Warm-Up	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energising the participants • Activating the participants' pre-knowledge on the meet-up's respective topic • Finding out about the participants' connections to the topic
10 – 20 minutes	Impulse talk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introducing an Open Science-related topic to those with little or no pre-knowledge on the topic • Providing perspectives/approaches to a topic for those already involved in the topic. • Providing a basis for the subsequent discussion
15 – 20 minutes	Questions and discussion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing space for questions on the impulse talk and the topic in general • Getting to know further perspectives, approaches and initiatives on the topic

2.1. Involving Warm-Ups

After gradually developing the idea of starting every session with a brief, playful warm-up, we decided to stick with that element. We did so because we felt that the idea of the warm-ups energising the participants worked out very well; an impression backed-up scientifically by Krueger and Minet (2022). Besides that, wherever suitable we involved elements related to activating the participants' pre-knowledge on the sessions' scopes, effectively connecting the participants' wide range of different backgrounds with the topics and thereby preparing them for the subsequent impulse

talks and the discussions. In a similar vein, by activating the participants' pre-knowledge, we continued, wherever suitable, trying to work out people's connections to the respective topics. We did so because we appreciated how that gave everyone an overview of the participants' backgrounds: It familiarised the participants with the groups' compositions as a preparation for the subsequent discussion, it gave the impulse speakers an idea on what to emphasize in their talks and it gave us as organisers an idea about what (not) to involve in the discussion. In the following, we will present some of the warm-up formats we regularly used. For more ideas on interactive formats for virtual events, we recommend the German-language *Veranstaltungskonzept* published by open-access.network (2022).

2.1.1. Counting to Twenty

The activity is rather easy to explain: You count to twenty as a group, the participants count up the numbers individually. If two participants say the same number at the same time, the count goes back to square one. This can be repeated multiple times, depending on how well it goes and how quickly the participants limber up.

This activity proved to be especially suitable in meet-ups with topics that suggested to us little or no pre-knowledge on the participants' part as even participants with no Open Science-related knowledge can join in effortlessly. Besides that, the activity is entertaining, playful and a lot of fun, thus allowing for a rather good incipient group spirit.

2.1.2. Chains of Associations

In this activity, the person chairing the session provides a term and mentions another participant's name. This person provides a term they associate with the chairperson's term and say another participant's name. That second participant, in turn, provides the next term and states a third person's name. The activity continues in this fashion until all participants have provided their associations.

This activity works independently from the participants' pre-knowledge as, even if Open Science terms are used, people can still associate non-Open Science-related terms. At the same time, by employing an Open Science term, the chairperson can get a limited grasp of whether or not there is pre-knowledge on Open Science in the group; especially if people keep using Open Science-related words. This activity, too,

is entertaining and playful. As everyone's involvement is rather spontaneous, it entails that people need to be alert from the beginning. This means that they have to think on their feet, which energises them in an effective fashion.

As the person chairing the session, one needs to bear in mind technical difficulties, such as disfunctional microphones, which may slow the activity down. Moreover, it is important to maintain an overview of the group with regards to who has already contributed their associations, as especially at a later stage people are likely to lose track of who has already had their turn. Due to these circumstances, we strongly recommend the organiser to stay alert at all times, as it is very important that they be able to step in quickly - not only for the success of the activity, but also to make sure that people do not feel uneasy if their microphones do not work or if they lose track of who has already been involved.

2.1.3. Word Clouds

Word clouds are an effective and optically attractive way of visualising points, such as aspects of people's pre-knowledge on a meet-up's topic. Unlike the first two activities, this is not a verbal, but a mainly visual activity. Usually, word clouds employ multiple colours, effectively clustering terms based on colour-coding. By using a range of different font sizes, they highlight frequently-mentioned terms. In the context of the meet-ups, we used the tool *Mentimeter* (www.menti.com).

This activity is playful and fun, also involving on a low-threshold basis quiet people who may be hesitant to engage in verbal-dominated warm-ups. At the same time, word clouds are a very efficient way of visualising a group's standpoints on whatever question or topic.

2.1.4. Whiteboard or Chat Associations

Similar to word clouds, interactive whiteboards can be used to gather a group's perspectives on a topic in a visual fashion; unlike word clouds, this relates not only to key points, but also to larger statements like sentences. Besides whiteboards, this activity can also be conducted using the Zoom chat. Like word clouds, this activity is suitable especially when it comes to involving quiet people. As we will describe later, we used a similar activity to the whiteboard in this activity when preparing post-impulse talk discussions. When using whiteboards, we recommend using the Zoom

whiteboards that have become part of the programme's portfolio as this means that the participants do not have to operate two tabs at the same time. In the course of the Re:ERUA project, we did the chat variant of this activity only twice and neither of these occasions proved to be very fruitful. This may tie in with participants having a harder time to find the chat than finding the shared whiteboard. However, we consider it more likely that the relative lack of anonymity compared to the whiteboard may keep people from using the chat in this activity.

2.1.5. Surveys

Surveys, which can be implemented very easily on Zoom, are a very good way of finding out about your participants' standpoints and perspectives, e.g. their pre-knowledge, their opinions on a certain topic, but also their adherence to a range of different target groups. The use of surveys, if employed in the right fashion, can be a highly informative, but also highly visual activity which also involves quiet participants on a low-threshold basis.

When using surveys on Zoom, we recommend saving every question as individual surveys as that means that you can show the results of every question individually. Saving all of your questions in one survey means that you have to display the results of all questions at the same time. This may distract the participants from the individual question you would like to discuss.

2.2. Providing Impulse Talks

As we were satisfied in the first set of meet-ups with how the impulse talks introduced Open Science-related topics to those with little or no pre-knowledge, we decided to stick with that concept. Besides that, we appreciated how the impulse talks provided (alternative) perspectives or approaches on topics to participants already involved in them. As far as both levels of Open Science-related awareness are concerned, we liked how the impulse talks provided a basis for the subsequent discussions. To provide the discussions with a multi-faceted range of perspectives that mirrors the diversity within Open Science, we carefully selected our speakers, involving both Open Science professionals and researchers from a range of different disciplines and institutions. To make sure enough time remained for the meet-ups' interactive parts, we limited the impulse talks to a maximum of 20 minutes. We shall elaborate on the

individual sessions, their scopes and the speakers involved in chapter 3, *Individual Meet-Up Instalments*.

2.3. Inviting Questions and Discussions

From the beginning, it was important for us to think of the meet-ups as an interactive format of exchange, not a mere lecture series that, at best, allows for a rather unilateral sphere of exchange in the form of presentations.

In order to allow for informed discussions after the impulse talks, we always focussed first on any questions the participants might (still) be pondering before (organically) delving into discussions that grew from the questions. Sometimes, this organic transition to a discussion did not work and it is important to mention this varies from group to group and from topic to topic. To cope with that, at some stage we started preparing whiteboards before the sessions to collect questions, associations and thoughts whenever we were dealing with topics we felt might be hard for the participants to engage in verbally. Whenever we had assessed the situation correctly, i.e. people did not ask questions or engage in a discussion verbally, we used these whiteboard to gather (initial) responses to boost the conversation. This two-step approach of first opening the floor with no additional material before involving whiteboards worked out rather well as forms of interactivity like whiteboards provide a low-threshold means of engaging quiet people, participants worrying about language-related barriers and people who were somewhat uncertain as to whether or not their questions or thoughts were worth mentioning in a verbal discussion. At the same time, this method did not cut down on the active participants' involvement. In these situations, we usually gave the participants some time to write down their points without verbal distractions before addressing the comments and, wherever suitable, asking the participants to elaborate on individual points without inviting anyone to do so by name. At some stage during the last two years, the interactive whiteboards became, as previously mentioned, a part of Zoom's portfolio. When that was the case, we soon chose to use the new Zoom whiteboards instead of the Miro whiteboards we had used previously. This had the advantage of enabling us to share our whiteboards just like presentations, entailing that the participants did not have to operate two tabs (Zoom and the Miro whiteboard) at the same time anymore, which enhanced the meet-ups' usability and interactivity especially for participants who did not have two screens at their disposal.

3. Individual Meet-Up Instalments

We dedicated the first meet-up after the ones described in our first publication to the topic **Repositories**. This topic suggested itself as repositories – storage services for digital objects – are among the most important building blocks of Open Science and, among other things, integral for self-archiving texts that may so far have been under restricted access. Apart from that, we decided to provide insight into how KonDATA (https://kondata.uni-konstanz.de/index_en.html), the University of Konstanz' institutional research data repository, was developed. We did so assuming that the University of Konstanz' experiences would be especially relevant for Open Science professionals from universities without institutional repositories. Here, we teamed up with a University of Konstanz Team Open Science staff member who was well versed in repository organisation and curation, having, among other things, had an important role in KonDATA's creation and curation. As this meet-up had 20 participants and was thus one of the most successful ones up to then, we reckoned that our intuition about repositories as a suitable topic for the meet-ups' had been right. Confirming our assumptions, a researcher reached out to the University of Konstanz' Open Science Team in the meet-up's aftermath, directly referring to this meet-up's input, with questions about how to best publish their research data. Not only did this confirm to us again the topic's relevance – it also demonstrated that, via the meet-ups, we managed to reach researchers we might otherwise not have reached.

As we expected everyone to be away for **Christmas** during our usual meet-up slot, each month's last Thursday afternoon, we decided to bring 2022's last meet-up forward by a couple of weeks. In addition to changing the time slot, we decided to seize the occasion of the ending year to **look back** to what we had covered so far and – at the same time – to **shed lights on our plans for the next year**. Discussing covered – and still to be covered – ground, we decided to seize the opportunity, using this session to find out about the participants' ideas as to what they would like the meet-ups to cover in future sessions. In this vein, we wanted to make sure that the meet-ups remained tailored to the participants' interests. The rest of the session, we decided, would be dedicated to a **game** to end the year on a fun note while still raising awareness of Open Science in a playful fashion. In the game, we wanted to provide the participants with sets of images that, if looked at together in a creative fashion, turned into a word related to either Open Science or Christmas. Here, it

would be the participants' task to find out which words were behind the images and – more easily – the words' relation to Open Science or Christmas. In this meet-up, we decided to stray from the normal structure, allotting the same amount of time to the inquiry part and the game. This meet-up saw the participation of only seven participants, which may have to do with the upcoming Christmas Break or the fact that most people were already working to their full capacity in the time before Christmas. Regardless, the discussion on potential future meet-up topics still proved somewhat fruitful and we ended up with some ideas for the next year. Apart from that, the fact that the majority of our participants were either colleagues from our Re:ERUA work package on Open Science or colleagues from the University of Konstanz' Team Open Science meant that the game contributed to our collegial work atmosphere.

After dedicating the majority of the 2022 meet-ups to rather librarian Open Science-related topics, we decided to cover in the first 2023 meet-up a topic related to what one could think of as applied Open Science: **Digital Procedures for Citation Analysis**. In this meet-up, an academic from the University of Konstanz' Department of Latin Studies presented how she (further) developed and evaluated digital procedures for citation analysis (Revellio, 2022). In the same vein, she discussed how Open Science was involved in her research. As this was an applied, and thus rather subject-specific, scope of Open Science, we did not expect this meet-up to have as many participants as some of the non-discipline-specific topics. However, the meet-up still had ten participants who engaged in a lively discussion. To us as organisers, this indicated that our approach of not only involving general Open Science topics was adequate as, maybe especially for researchers, Open Science may be at its most graspable when discussed in the context of (subject-)specific use cases. In a similar fashion, we decided to dedicate the next meet-up to an education-related topic: **Open Science and the Reform Universities' Paradigm**. After a Bulgarian researcher working at the interface of the two topics had suggested it for a meet-up, offering to provide the impulse talk, we immediately agreed to go for that topic. In a similar fashion as with the previous instalment, this meet-up did not attract as many participants as most of the rather general Open Science topics. However, like in the previous meet-up, the seven participants who turned up engaged in a meaningful discussion. Moreover, and again in a similar fashion as with the previous

meet-up, three of the seven participants were professors who might otherwise not have been in touch with Open Science (that way).

The next meet-up was, again, about one of the more librarian aspects of Open Science: **Open Access Consortia** and the funding models behind Diamond Open Access that go with them. As, at least in Germany, consortia-related funding models are on the rise to get rid of Open Access-related publication charges for authors, we thought of such models as a topic worth presenting and discussing (UNESCO, 2024). In this meet-up, we teamed up with two Team Open Science colleagues from the University of Konstanz who, back then, were involved in an Open Access Consortia-related project (Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology University Library, n.d.). This meet-up saw the participation of nine individuals who were eager to ask questions about the University of Konstanz' consortia involvements presented and to discuss and share resources. They can be found on the meet-ups' website (*Open Science Meet-Ups*, n.d.).

Subsequently, we dedicated three meet-ups to topics related to raising and spreading awareness on Open Science. We considered that issue paramount as Open Science gaining in momentum entails a growing need to raise awareness on the movement and its many facets beyond librarian spheres. The first of these topics was **Teaching Open Science**, as through teaching both researchers and academic support staff can get a more ample grasp of what impact Open Science can have on their professional lives and thus, why it is so important. Here, we joined forces with a colleague from Roskilde University who specialises in research data management and has copious experience teaching this subfield of Open Science. The subsequent meet-up covered a somewhat less intuitive topic: **Performing Open Science**. We addressed that topic as, at least in our experience, Open Science professionals oftentimes tend to have a hard time being heard by a wider audience – which may, among other things, have to do with the researchers' workload. This suggests that new, somewhat entertaining approaches to communication may be helpful, such as questions revolving around how Science Slams can be a suitable format to convey Open Science to a larger audience. Here, a University of Konstanz' Team Open Science colleague with plenty of practical experience with Science Slams agreed to provide some insight into his experiences with the format. The third of these meet-ups was about **Open Science Information Portals**. We addressed that topic having

observed that the field of Open Science' vastness can be somewhat intimidating for those new to the movement. At the same time, there is a need for awareness and the information that goes with it – not only on the part of new Open Science professionals, but also on the part of researchers who, among other things, would like to publish their texts Open Access or get an introduction to the principles of research data management. As the University of Konstanz is a driving force behind two paramount national Open Science-related information platforms called [open-access.network](#) and [forschungsdaten.info](#), we felt that presenting these platforms could prove helpful – both for those who may not already know them and with regards to finding out together which other information portals there are across the alliance and the countries represented in it. Here, the main meet-up organiser, who is also head of [forschungsdaten.info](#), and one of his colleagues, who, back then, had a leading editorial role at [open-access.network](#), provided a joint impulse talk. Some time before the meet-up, a colleague from Bulgaria suggested to additionally introduce the [Bulgarian Portal for Open Science](#), which we gladly accepted. The fact that there are different portals on Open Science across the EU and the different scopes they cover again confirmed to us the need for exchange in order to learn from each other, and underlines that EUI-related alliances are a good forum for that kind of exchange. All of these three meet-ups were visited by 14 participants who engaged in fruitful discussions, eager to contribute experiences and to share helpful links. These links can be found on the website (*Open Science Meet-Ups*, n.d.)

As the summer time was approaching, we decided to play an **Open Science Summer Game** in the last meet-up before the summer break and the absence of a meet-up in August that went with it. The concept behind the game was to provide the participants with words in which the letters had been mixed up and to let them unravel the words. As clues, we told the participants that the words related to Open Science or summer. Apart from that, we gave them two pictures per word, one offering a clue and one misleading them. As in the Christmas Meet-up, the number of participants was rather scarce with only seven individuals, but those who were there (again mainly Open Science-related colleagues of the organisers) were eager to engage in the game, which again enhanced the collegial atmosphere and provided a good start into the summer break.

The subsequent meet-up took place in late September and was dedicated to the topic **Data Quality**. We chose that topic due to the circumstance that, in the context of research data management, only high-quality data is useful enough to merit re-use, which entails that data quality should be a paramount factor when publishing research data. In this meet-up, the University of Konstanz' Head of Open Science, who is well versed in the principles behind data quality, agreed to provide the impulse talk. This meet-up saw the participation of 15 participants, which confirmed this topic to us as a relevant topic in Open Science, as is research data management in general. In view of that and as research data management is a highly complex field, the organisers decided after this meet-up to dedicate a number of meet-up sessions in the final year of Re:ERUA to the subfield of research data management. These will be discussed later.

After the 2023 ERUA Summit – and the absence of a virtual meet-up in October 2023 that went with it – we dedicated the next meet-up to **Virtual Research Environments**. We chose that topic as virtual research environments are, at least in Germany, among the lesser-known fields of Open Science, which entails that the topic deserves scrutiny and exchange. Here, we teamed up with a colleague from the University of Konstanz' Team Open Science who, back then, specialised in the topic. This was one of the few meet-ups where the person giving the impulse talk drafted the follow-up activity, presenting a range of different technologies and asking the participants whether or not, in their opinion, the respective technologies qualified as virtual research environments. Here, our speaker used the meet-up in a synergetic fashion to get input on definition-related questions revolving around virtual research environments that he had been pondering before. This example illustrates how, in the sense of exchange, the meet-ups served as a means of using the forum of the alliance as a means of dealing with people's work-related Open Science questions, effectively contributing to the movement's development. In this meet-up, we ended up having 20 participants, which indicated to us that we had been right in assuming virtual research environment as a relevant topic for Open Science enthusiasts from across the alliance.

As in 2022, we decided to play an **Open Science and Christmas Game** in the year's final meet-up. However, unlike in 2022, we decided not to ask the participants for topic-related requests for the next meet-ups as we still had many ideas for the final

project year. Moreover, feeling that it had been pleasant in July to dedicate the whole summer session to the game, we chose to go with that again. In that year's Christmas Game, we provided the participants with two texts per round, one from a Christmas carol and one from Open Science-related glossaries. In both texts, either a word or a number of words were missing. The idea was to first let the participants guess which of the texts related to Open Science and which to Christmas. Then they had to fill in the blanks and to have a guess about to which Christmas carols and which Open Science phenomena the texts related. Similar to the previous year's Christmas meet-up, this meet-up saw the participation of about eight people, most of them colleagues, contributing – just like in previous years – to our collegial working atmosphere.

In 2024, we dedicated the first meet-up to **Pitfalls of Open Access and How to Handle Them**. We decided to discuss that topic after one of the ERUA Open Science ambassadors that we had appointed over the course of the project had suggested it to us. He argued that informing academics about pitfalls related to Open Access was essential for convincing them to pursue Open Access publications as only by clearly explaining the pitfalls can Open Science professionals hope to address the academics' pitfalls-related reservations in a convincing fashion. Along these lines, the ambassador, who is well versed in and enthusiastic about Open Access, offered to provide this meet-ups' impulse talk. This session saw the participation of about 15 individuals who eagerly asked questions after the talk and discussed this topic as well as adjacent topics. This suggested to us that our ambassador's intuition about this topic being highly relevant had been right.

After this meet-up, we decided to talk about research data management, as we had already planned in 2023. As research data management, at least from a German point of view, is growing in terms of importance and complexity, we decided to stick with our late 2022 plans, dedicating multiple sessions to the topic in order to look at the phenomenon's individual aspects in a more ample fashion than what would have been possible in one session. As a starting point, we decided to introduce the topic on a rather general scale in a session called **Research Data Management and Open Science**. Here, we joined forces with a colleague from Roskilde University who has plenty of experience with general introductions to research data management. This session was visited by 17 participants who eagerly asked their questions on

research data management. The number of people and their obvious interest confirmed to us that research data management was indeed a relevant topic for the alliance. After this rather general introduction, we decided to delve into the infrastructural dimension behind research data management in a meet-up called **Better Together – The Political and Networking Dimension of Research Data Management**. We chose that subtopic as Germany tends to perceive research data management as a “team sport”. This relates to the fact that no infrastructural player is able to do research data management entirely on their own – as the field, especially in terms of different kinds of data as well as the requirements and conditions that go with them, is much too vast and too multi-faceted for that. In view of that, research institutions across Germany have joined forces in the NFDI (*Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur*, national research data Infrastructure, <https://www.nfdi.de/>). As this kind of infrastructure is rare across Europe, we thought it a topic worth discussing as a means of inspiration for countries may not yet have a similar structure. In this vein, we teamed up for the impulse presentation with a colleague from the University of Konstanz’ Team Open Science who works in the NFDI. This meet-up saw the participation of 11 individuals. To wrap up the series of research data management-related meet-ups, we organised a panel discussion on **Research Data Management Across Countries**. Here, we teamed up with three research data management-related specialists from our Open Science work package who agreed to contribute their country-specific perspectives from Germany, Denmark and France as panellists. We chose that topic to find out how the definitions and thus the scopes of research data management vary across Europe and thus to provide everyone with intercultural impulses for their work. This meet-up saw the participation of 20 individuals who were eager to ask their questions and to share their perspectives on research data management, which again underlined our notion that there is a high demand for exchanging perspectives on Open Science across countries and cultures. As we had decided to dedicate the session’s main part fully to the panel discussion, we again chose to stray from the usual structure, doing without impulse presentations.

As our previously mentioned ERUA Open Science Ambassador Programme (European Reform Universities Alliance, 2024) was picking up speed in spring 2024, we dedicated a meet-up to it. One idea behind this was meet-up was to raise awareness of the programme and to delineate it to those in the alliance interested in

Open Science. Apart from that, having so far only dedicated one meet-up to open educational resources, we decided to revisit that topic in an ambassadorial context. Here, we teamed up with the University of Konstanz' Open Science ambassador who agreed to provide an impulse talk on **Open Educational Resources within the ERUA Open Science Ambassador Programme: A Best Practice Example**. This meet-up saw the participation of 20 individuals who were eager to ask questions and to engage in a meaning discussion. In fact, even before the meet-up took place, the organisers were called by an Open Science professional specialising in Open Educational Resources who was so intrigued by this meet-up's scope that she enquired whether she was allowed to promote the meet-up further in her network of Open Science professionals. We strongly appreciated her call, eagerly agreeing with her kind offer. To us, this showed that the exchange-related offering shaped within the ERUA Open Science Meet-Ups comes with a relevance that exceeds the sphere of ERUA. On that basis, we decided to look into how our sphere of exchange could expand beyond the alliance as a cross-alliance forum for Open Science exchange. We shall elaborate later on what became of that idea.

As the final Re:ERUA Meet-Ups before the project's close in September 2024, we decided to go for an **Open Science Summer Game Reloaded** in July and a wrap-up-related meet-up in late September called **Three Years of European Universities Initiative Open Science: Recap and Outlook**. The meet-up in July revisited the previous Christmas Game, involving summer hits from the last decades instead of Christmas carols. It saw the participation of ten individuals and, just like the previous games, enhanced our collegial work atmosphere. In this meet-up, we looked back to which grounds we had covered over the course of the project duration in the meet-ups, the project's further deliverables and, moving beyond the scope of the project, Open Science-related developments in other EUI alliances. Along these lines, we looked at where we could go from here, both within the individual alliances and beyond. This ties with the University of Konstanz' plan to not only continue the Open Science Meet-Ups beyond the Re:ERUA project in the context of the alliance EUniWell (n.d.). We shall elaborate on these plans in more detail at a later stage.

4. Communicating the Meet-Ups

After detailing the individual meet-ups' content and their participant numbers, it is important to address how we wanted potential interested parties to find out about this format.

Just like the first nine meet-ups, all instalments discussed in this publication were promoted through the following University of Konstanz-specific channels:

- The university's local ERUA website and its calendar
- The Communication, Information and Media Centre's website news
- The university's event calendar and event newsletter
- The university's Open Science-related mailing list
- The International Office's Instagram channel
- The university's general newsletter EINBLICK

An important resource we continued using to list and document each meet-up - whenever suitable with material, outcomes or relevant links from the discussions - was the local meet-up website for the Open Science Meet-Ups at the University of Konstanz (*Open Science Meet-Ups*, n.d.). This site provides a chronological list of all meet-ups past and upcoming. Apart from that, we continued promoting the meet-ups via the project's Open Science work package-related mailing list as well as the mailing list we had set up specifically for the meet-ups. After the first meet-up, we had decided not to continue promoting the subsequent eight meet-ups via the EINBLICK, as this newsletter is not intended for regularly occurring events, but single instant-related news and announcements. Regarding the 28 meet-ups discussed in this publication, we chose to stick with that decision. However, over time, we chose to employ additional channels. This refers to the central ERUA newsletter, as it came into being, and the German social media platform Mastodon, as that platform grew in importance after Elon Musk's acquisition of Twitter/X, which led to many academics abandoning Twitter in favour of Mastodon. At some stage, our promotion-related aims went beyond ERUA, which meant that we were broadening the target audience to include Open Science enthusiasts from other alliances and beyond. This idea essentially coincided with the creation of an EU-wide mailing list called [FOR-EU Libraries Mailing list](#) in 2023 and the low-threshold opportunity that went with it to reach out internationally to academic librarians interested in Open Science. We first

employed this mailing list - with immediate success – when promoting the meet-up on Data Quality, which took place in September 2023. After the University of Konstanz joined EUniWell in November 2023, we additionally promoted the meet-ups to this alliance’s Open Science work package. Around the same time, new members joined the alliance ERUA, whom we also involved in our promotion-related measures.

At some stage, we expanded the meet-ups’ visual promotion. In this vein, we developed a consistent visual language, featuring instalment-specific recognizable graphics that included not only the title and event details but also a content-related illustration to capture the potential participants’ interest (Image 1). While the visuals’ right side consistently displayed the titles and event details, we tailored the left side to match each session’s specific content. These visuals replaced the logo we had previously used (Image 2). In addition to the enhanced recognition value created by this visual branding, this helped present the information in a visually engaging format, catering to those who prefer visuals over text.

Image 1: The new visual (Canva Free License, not CC-BY) Image 2: The first logo

From this point onward, the visuals enhanced our promotion-related efforts in the following channels:

- The University of Konstanz’s social media channels (Instagram, X/Twitter, Mastodon, LinkedIn)
- ERUA’s event calendar and website news
- ERUA’s social media channels (Instagram, Facebook, LinkedIn)

Expanding the channels we were employing, we also adapted the visuals’ formats as well as the language register according to each channel’s specifics: While texts for websites and mailing lists can be more extensive, social media often imposes strict

character limits. This constraint requires distilling content to its essence, which, in turn, allows for more effective communication with the target audience. Moreover, we were careful to format the visuals according to the media's specific requirements.

At the meet-up in September 2023, we conducted a survey (Image 3) along with the warm-up session to better understand the target audience and to determine which channels the participants had used to learn about the event. Here, our participants were allowed to tick all boxes that applied to them. According to the survey results, 36% of this instalment's attendees had found out about the meet-up through mailing lists, and an equal percentage (36%) had learned about it via social media. Only 9% reported obtaining information from the ERUA website, either through the calendar or news section. Interestingly, 64% of participants had heard about the meet-ups from colleagues, while 18% had been informed through other channels within their own institution. Additionally, 55% mentioned having been informed by the organizer. The survey demonstrated that expanding our promotion-related efforts to additional channels had been successful, so we decided to continue using them.

Meet-Up Find Out

Image 3: Survey

5. Outlook

Over the course of the 28 ERUA Open Science Meet-Ups, we covered a diverse and multi-faceted range of Open Science-related ground, involving as impulse speakers and participants Open Science professionals and researchers from several different countries, related to a multitude of academic disciplines and Open Science-related subtopics. The range of issues we addressed and the gradually growing number of

participants as well as their eagerness to engage in the discussions confirmed to us that there is a high demand of cross-national exchange on Open Science.

Along these lines, the meet-up organisers have decided that the alliance EUniWell, of which the University of Konstanz is now a member, will pick up the thread of the Open Science Meet-Ups after the end of the Re:ERUA project. Even though, as of now, it is uncertain whether or not the virtual Open Science Meet-Ups will carry on, in the long run, as the monthly event established in the Re:ERUA project, the next sessions have already been planned and scheduled (*Open Science Meet-Ups*, n.d.). For continuity reason, the current meet-up website will continue to be used. Apart from carrying on with the meet-ups, the University of Konstanz and the alliance EUniWell pursue plans to expand the meet-ups beyond the frame of ERUA even more than we during the Re:ERUA project duration. This ties in with our successful use of channels like the For-EU mailing list, involving agents across the EU, rendering our discussions even more multi-faceted and useful than before. Along these lines, it is our intent to offer and establish the meet-ups as a cross-alliance forum of exchange open not only for members of ERUA and EUniWell, but to Open Science enthusiasts everywhere.

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